

SECURITY MARKET OVERVIEW: TECNOSEC & DRONEXPO EVENT

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
APTIE	Asociación para la Promoción de las Tecnologías e Industrias Estratégicas
AR	Analytical Report
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
CERIS	Community of European R&I for Security
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CIRT	Computer Incident Response Team
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EC	European Commission
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight against Crime and Terrorism
FR	Flash Report
IoT	Internet-of-Things
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
R&D&I	Research, Development and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SOP	Security Operations Centre
TECNOSEC	Altas Tecnologías de Seguridad e Inteligencia, Drones y Antidrones

TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024: Overview

TECNOSEC [1] has evolved into the premier professional forum for police, intelligence, and security technologies since its inception. Held annually in Madrid, this event, sponsored by Telefónica, Indra, Bluenest, Zebra, and Ineco, provides a centralised platform for the most significant business opportunities among a growing array of specialised technological solutions.

In an era where public-private collaboration is paramount for developing new capabilities through coordinated R&D&I initiatives between governmental bodies, development companies, and research centres, TECNOSEC serves as a focal point for major security stakeholders. It facilitates the exchange of knowledge and trends, presenting practical works and products tailored for security and intelligence bodies and critical infrastructures.

Organised by APTIE under the institutional sponsorship of the Ministry of the Interior, TECNOSEC stands as a reference showcase for high technologies. It highlights advancements in Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Big Data, New Platforms and Sensors, Cybersecurity, Identification and Biometrics, Data and Image Analysis, 5G Communications, and other solutions vital for national security, counter-terrorism, economic and industrial intelligence, and combating organised crime.

The event draws significant institutional support, ensuring the attendance of top authorities, middle managers, and technicians from various Spanish governmental agencies, such as Ministry of the Interior, Civil Guard, National Police, National Intelligence Centre, and security forces. It has a diverse representation of directors or representatives from police forces across different Autonomous Communities, municipalities in Spain, security and technology managers from various sectors, owners of critical infrastructures, users of both physical and logical security. TECNOSEC connects all stakeholders, attracting directors, executives, technicians, and sales representatives from both national and foreign companies involved in the supply and acquisition of security equipment and services.

TECNOSEC exhibition took place together with the DRONExpo fair [2], which is focused on drone and anti-drone technologies, and associated applications. This partnership is a great complement in such an important field of unmanned aerial, land, underwater and surface platforms, which are increasingly integral to the operations of various security entities.

[1] TECNOSEC 2024 event website: <https://www.tecnosec.es/en/>

[2] DRONExpo 2024 event website: <https://www.dronexpo.es/en/>

A view on the Security Market

The 3rd edition of TECNOSEC & DRONExpo featured over 100 exhibiting companies, welcomed more than 4000 professional visitors, hosted over 80 speakers across various panel discussions and commercial presentations [3]. As part of the “Brokerage Event” organised by the EEN and Madri+d, more than 150 meetings were held, fostering valuable networking opportunities and collaboration within the industry. Several Spanish authorities attended the event to witness the latest technologies showcased by sector companies, designed for diverse security applications and intended for use by security forces, intelligence agencies, and the Armed Forces, among others.

To provide a thorough analysis of the showcased technologies and their significance within the broader context of security market trends and needs, this report systematically correlates exhibitor profiles and conference themes with the EU Security Market Taxonomy [4]. This approach ensures the acquisition of a quantitative and comparable assessment, serving as a reference for guiding future R&I programming.

TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024: Exhibitors

TECNOSEC exhibition [5] and DRONExpo fair [6] bring together the leading technology companies in the sector, offering a comprehensive array of technology products and services tailored for security, intelligence and safeguarding critical infrastructures. Particularly, DRONExpo is the benchmark meeting for professionals in the drone industry, specifically tailored to the Spanish market, offering insights into the unmanned technological future.

The TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024 event is structured around the technological sectors outlined in Table 1 below.

[3] News and media: <https://www.elradar.es/visitantes-tecnosec-dronexpo-2024/>

[4] European Commission – EU security market study. Available at: https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/eu-security-market-study_en

[5] TECNOSEC exhibitor profile: <https://www.tecnosec.es/en/exhibitor-profile>

[6] DRONExpo exhibitor profile: <https://www.dronexpo.es/en/exhibitor-profile/>

Event	Technological sectors	Sub-areas
TECNOSEC	Police, security and intelligence technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agent Protection • Technologies for the integration, analysis and management of operational and documentary information (big data, AI, biometrics, virtual and augmented reality, etc.) • Intelligence against organized and financial crime • Counterterrorism intelligence
	Communications, Command and Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure communications • Mobility in communications • Management of operating units • Disaster management
	Scientific and Criminal Police	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratory equipment • Mobile and personal laboratories • DNA • Zone analysis technologies
	Platforms and sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drones, anti-drones and robots • Police vehicles • On board equipment • Detection sensors
	Cybersecurity: Cyber defence and Cybersec	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection, monitoring, defence and response technologies • Anti-malware, monitoring and forensic software • Secured hardware, cryptographic, firewall and ruggedised • High security level critical physical infrastructure and hosting services • SOP, CSIRT, CERT, CIRT
	Critical infrastructure protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facility Protection • CBRN • Detection and protection against explosives
	Border security and major events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coast and sea detection and protection technologies • People Identification Technologies • Documentation security technologies. blockchain • Baggage inspection and control
DRONExpo	Platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial • Terrestrial • Submarines • Of surface
	Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control software • Sector systems • Interoperability • U space
	Payloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optical cameras • Infrared cameras • Sensors
	Anti-drone systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection • Identification • Neutralization

Table 1 – Exhibitors’ profile

Out of a total of 95 exhibitors, 81 (85%) were identified as pertinent to the FCT domain and are detailed in Appendix A. As depicted in Figures 1 and 2, the exhibiting private companies relevant for FCT domain have been mapped according to the EU Security Market taxonomy in the Functions and Technology domains. This classification aids in discerning how the market's offerings at the event aligns with established R&I priorities and trends, providing valuable insights for strategic planning and development within the FCT sector (see Appendix A for more information).

Regarding the coverage of FCT functions (see Figure 1), **monitoring and surveillance of environments and activities** function stands out as the most addressed element of the function dimension, covered by a total of 41 companies. Exhibitors also prominently featured functions related to **data, information & intelligence gathering, and exploitation; mobility and deployability**; and **secure and public communication, data and information exchange**, while **positioning and localisation, tracking and tracing and personal and other equipment for prevention, response and recovery** functions were least represented, ranking the 11th and 12th positions, respectively.

For comparison, it is important to analyse the FCT functions against the ENACT AR on “EU FCT R&I priorities 2014-2024” [7], which reviews a total of 76 topics (including subtopics) published by the EC in the FCT domain, to understand if the event aligns with the FCT R&I priorities of the EC. In the AR, the four main identified functions appear in the 7th, 2nd, 12th (last), and 5th positions, respectively, while the two functions with poor representation in the exhibition appear in 11th and 8th places, respectively. Comparing these results, despite occasional disparities with the priorities of the EU-funded R&I programme, particularly in **monitoring and surveillance of environments and activities** and **mobility and deployability** functions, the overall functions taxonomy elements addressed by exhibitors aligns fairly with the established priorities. Notably, data, information & intelligence gathering, and exploitation and secure and public communication, data and information exchange functions perfectly overlap with the identified FCT R&I priorities of the EC. Furthermore, this alignment shows a better match of the market offerings at TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024 event than the previous FR on the SICUR exhibition [8].

[7] Analytical Report 01 – FCT R&I: An Analysis of EU Priorities 2014-2024: <https://enact-eu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ENACT-Analytical-Report-01-FCT-RI-An-analysis-of-EU-priorities-2014-2024.pdf>

[8] Flash Report 01 – Security Market Overview: Trends & Insights from the SICUR Exhibition: <https://enact-eu.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ENACT-FLASH-REPORT-1-SICUR-exhibition.pdf>

Figure 1 – Mapping of the exhibiting private companies in the Functions domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

In the technology domain (see Figure 2), and in correlation with the analysis above in the functions domain, **surveillance systems** largely surpassed other technologies in terms of representation at the event, with 44 exhibitors. The next most represented technologies were **data analytics** and **critical communications, interoperable communications**, with equal representation (22 exhibitors each), and **digital security products and services** (21 exhibitors). There are no references to **search devices and tools, monitoring tools and services, guarding and physical protection**, or **facilitation systems and secure databases** technologies.

Analysing the technologies represented at TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024 event against the mapping of research topics to the technology dimension of the EU Security Market Study taxonomy done in the ENACT AR, there are some mismatches between the identified technologies and defined EC priorities. **Data analytics** and **critical communications, interoperable communications** technologies are well aligned with EC priorities, occupying the 2nd and 5th position on the list of topics by technology area. On the other hand, **surveillance systems** and **digital security products and services** were largely overrepresented, ranking the 9th and 10th position, respectively. The technologies with the least representation in the exhibition correspond to those with minimal to no interest in the FCT research topics. Therefore, to effectively address the identified R&I gaps in FCT, greater attention should be placed on future TECNOSEC & DRONEXPO events, as the event was more closely aligned with the EU FCT R&I agenda compared to SICUR exhibition, which primarily focuses on **access control/authorisation** (8th place in FCT topics).

Figure 2 – Mapping of the exhibiting private companies in the Technology domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

TECNOSEC & DRONExpo 2024: Conferences

The two-day event, held in Madrid, brought together experts and stakeholders from various fields to discuss the latest advancements and needs in security and technology. The sessions covered a broad range of topics, emphasising the integration of advanced technologies to enhance public safety and security. The list of TECNOSEC [9] and DRONExpo sessions [10] relevant to FCT (available in Appendix B) have been reviewed and mapped to the policy, functions, and technology taxonomy.

Of the 11 sessions, 8 covered key topics within FCT, discussing the evolution of emergency communication networks to broadband, cybersecurity including risk management, ransomware, IoT connectivity, multi-factor authentication, and digital identity. The role of artificial intelligence in automating crime processes, supporting criminology and forensics, and processing large data volumes was examined. Secure communications were addressed, focusing on encryption, 5G security, and interception. U-Space and its airspace security implications, the impact of new drone navigation regulations, anti-drone systems for event security, and urban air mobility development were also covered.

[9] TECNOSEC conferences: <https://www.tecnosec.es/sala-tecnosec/>

[10] DRONExpo 2024 sessions: <https://www.dronexpo.es/agenda/>

Considering the key topics identified in these sessions, they have a clear focus on **mobility and deployability** and **secure and public communication, data and information exchange** functions, alongside **decontamination and neutralisation** related to anti-drone systems, **security of information systems, networks and hardware**, among others. Additionally, the analysis highlights the emphasis on cybersecurity and information and communication technologies across the FCT functions. The sessions stress the importance of digital tools in supporting and being the subject of investigations. Moreover, discussions around drones, perceived both as assets and threats by LEAs, along with technologies like 5G, encryption, and public space security, further reinforce FCT-related themes.

Figure 3 – Mapping of the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo conferences in the Policy domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

FCT Functions

Figure 4 – Mapping of the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo conferences in the Functions domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

Technology areas

Figure 5 – Mapping of the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo conferences in the Technology domain, according to the EU Security Market taxonomy.

When comparing the functions representation and their alignment with FCT policy priorities between TECNOSEC & DRONEXPO and SICUR exhibitions, SICUR has widely stressed the importance of cybersecurity, whereas the former has focused extensively on the need for secure communication, particularly in the context of drones and counter drones' technologies.

Relevant insights

The TECNOSEC & DRONEXPO 2024 events are important representations for showcasing the current landscape of security market offerings in terms of technologies and functions for FCT, as well as serving as a forum for private and public actors to meet. Although smaller than the SICUR exhibition (also an important event for FCT), TECNOSEC is more closely aligned with the FCT R&I priorities than SICUR. This alignment could be exploited by FCT actors, particularly law enforcement, in order to fill the gaps perceived by the EC in the area of FCT. Additionally, these events serve as a fertile ground for generating new ideas and technologies that can inform and enhance future research topics.

In addition to SICUR, TECNOSEC and DRONEXPO, several other significant events are essential for the ENACT project and the broader FCT domain. It is important to keep monitoring and analysing these events to better understand market evolution, what are the current market priorities and discussions, and how these are aligned or mis-aligned with the FCT R&I priorities from the EU's funding programmes. A few events that could be of interest include the General Police Equipment Exhibition & Conference, the World Police Summit, ASIS Europe, Commercial UAV Expo Europe, Eurosatory, Milipol Paris, and the Future Forces Forum. This is not an exhaustive list of events, and as ENACT partners become aware of more events, then the monitoring of these events can take place after ensuring their relevance to the FCT domain.

By leveraging insights from these diverse events, ENACT can better align its efforts with market trends and the strategic priorities of the EU, thereby enhancing the effectiveness and impact of its initiatives in the FCT domain.

TECNOSEC & DRONExpo reference information

Name of the event: International Conference on High Security and Intelligence Technologies Fair; Professional Congress Fair of Platforms and Applications for Unmanned Systems

Dates: 8 May – 9 May 2024

Location: Pabellón de Cristal – Madrid – Spain

Website:

- <https://www.tecnosec.es/en/>
- <https://www.dronexpo.es/en/>

Relevant news:

- <https://www.tecnosec.es/noticias/>
- <https://www.dronexpo.es/noticias/>
- <https://www.elradar.es/visitantes-tecnosec-dronexpo-2024/>

APPENDIX A - TECNOSEC & DRONExpo Exhibitors

The following table shows the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo exhibitors that are relevant to the FCT domain and which have been used in the analysis presented in this report. The full mapping table is available via the [ENACT website](#). For detailed information regarding the exhibitors please refer to: <https://www.tecnosec.es/expositores/>; <https://www.dronexpo.es/expositores/>

Exhibitors	Event	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
ACCURO TECHNOLOGY (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://accuro.es
ADTEL (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity, Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.adtel.es/
AEROMEDIA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms, Anti-Drone Systems	https://www.aeromedia.es/
AHYRES (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://ahyres.com/
AIRBUS (France)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.airbus.com/
AMPED SOFTWARE (Italy)	TECNOSEC	Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://ampedsoftware.com/
AREXDATA (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity, Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.arexdata.com/
ATL EUROPA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.atleuropa.es/
AUTHUSB (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity, Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.authusb.net/
AVIAT NETWORKS (United States)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.aviatnetworks.com/
BLUENEST (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.bluenest.io/
CAMBIUM NETWORKS (United States)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.cambiumnetworks.com/
CANARD DRONES (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://canarddrones.com/
CASMAR (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.casmarglobal.com/
CELERWAY (Norway)	TECNOSEC	Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.celerway.com/
CELLEBRITE (United States)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity: Cyberdefense and Cybersec, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://cellebrite.com/

Exhibitors	Event	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
CICOMTEC SISTEMAS (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.cicomtec.com/
CROWTEC (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.crowtec.co/
DJI ARS MADRID (China)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.dji.com/es/
DOMO TACTICAL COMMUNICATIONS (United Kingdom)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.domotactical.com/
DRONE HOPPER (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.drone-hopper.es/
DRONESOLUTIONS (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.dronesolutions.es/
DRONICS TECHNOLOGY (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://dronics-technology.com/
ECAPTUREDTECH (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.ecapturedtech.com/
EPICOM (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.epicom.es/
ESRI (United States)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.esri.com/
ETRA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.grupoetra.com/
EXCEM TECHNOLOGIES (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.excem.es/
FUJIFILM ESPAÑA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.fujifilm.com/es/es-es
GETAC (Taiwan)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.getac.com/
HERTA (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.hertasecurity.com/
HEXAGON (United States)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.hexagonsafetyinfrastructure.com/
HIGH LINE DIVISION (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.highlinedivision.com/

Exhibitors	Event	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
HLD UNMANNED SYSTEMS (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://hldunmannedsystems.com/
IDEMIA (France)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity: Cyberdefense and Cybersec, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.idemia.com/
INDRA (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.indracompany.com/
INSEIN (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity, Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.inseinsl.com/
ISID (Japan)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.isid.com/
ITG (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.itg.es/
IVAQ (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://www.ivaq.es/
LEONARDO (Italy)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.leonardocompany.com/
MAGNET FORENSICS (Canada)	TECNOSEC	Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.magnetforensics.com/
MALTEGO (Germany)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity: Cyberdefense and Cybersec, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.maltego.com/
METROHM HISPANIA (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.metrohm.com/
MOBILIS (France)	TECNOSEC	Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.mobiliscase.com/en/
MOLLITIAM INDUSTRIES (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.mollitiamindustries.com/
MULTITECH (United States)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.multitech.com/
MVP CLUSTER (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Applications, Forensic and Criminalistics, Criminal Analysis Systems, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://mvpcluster.com/
ONDATA INTERNACIONAL (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.ondata.es/
ONRETRIEVAL (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.onretrieval.com/

Exhibitors	Event	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
OPTAGLIO (Czech Republic)	TECNOSEC	Authentication, Identification, Marketing, Border and Major Event Security, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.optaglio.com/
PANASONIC TOUGHBOOK (Japan)	TECNOSEC	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://eu.connect.panasonic.com/gb/en/toughbook
PROCESIA PROYECTOS Y SERVICIOS (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity: Cyberdefense and Cybersec	https://www.procesia.com
RED TEAM SHIELD (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Critical Infrastructure Protection	https://www.redteamshield.com/
REMOVE GROUP (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Online Reputation Cleaning	https://www.removegroup.com/
ROHDE & SCHWARZ ESPAÑA (Germany)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Communications, Command and Control, Police, Security, and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.rohde-schwarz.com/es/p-gina-principal_48230.html
SATCUBE (Sweden)	TECNOSEC	Portable Satellite Connection	https://satcube.com/
SEADRONE (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Design and Development of Unmanned Marine Vehicles	https://seadrone.es/
SISTELEC (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Security and Communication Solutions	https://www.sistelec.es/
SMARTHAPS (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Cybersecurity Solutions	https://smarthaps.com/
SONY (Japan)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Multimedia and Electronic Technology	https://www.sony.es/
SQUADRONE (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones and Anti-Drone Systems	https://www.squadrone.es/
SWARMING (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Cybersecurity Solutions	https://swarmingts.com/
SYSTEM DRONE ESPAÑA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones and Anti-Drone Systems	http://www.sdeweb.es/
TACTICALDRONE (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Pilot Training School	https://tacticaldrone.es/
TAIT COMMUNICATIONS (New Zealand)	TECNOSEC	Communications and Radio	https://www.taitradio.com/
TARGET TECNOLOGÍA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Technological Solutions	https://www.target-tecnologia.es/

Exhibitors	Event	Company self-description at SICUR website	URL
TASSTA (Germany)	TECNOSEC	Push-to-Talk Communications Technology	https://www.tassta.com/
TELEFÓNICA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Telecommunications and Services	https://www.telefonica.com/
THALES (France)	TECNOSEC	Security Technology and Solutions	https://www.thalesgroup.com/
TOWNET (Italy)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity Solutions	https://www.townet.it/
TRACK-NOISE (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Applications, Drones - Platforms, Critical Infrastructure Protection, Border and Major Event Security	https://www.tracknoise.com/
UAV WORKS (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Maritime/Fisheries Inspection and Security, Ad-Hoc Developments, Platforms and Sensors, Forensic and Criminalistics, Border and Major Event Security, Police Security and Intelligence Technologies	https://www.uavworks.es/
UNMANED MILES (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Drones - Platforms	https://umilesgroup.com/
UTEK (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Technological Solutions	https://www.utek.es/
VERIDAS (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Identity Verification Solutions	https://www.veridas.com/
VEXIZA (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity Solutions	https://vexiza.com/
VICOMTECH (Spain)	TECNOSEC	Research and Technology	https://www.vicomtech.org/
ZEBRA TECHNOLOGIES (United States)	TECNOSEC	Printing and Tracking Solutions	https://www.zebra.com/
ZELENA (Spain)	TECNOSEC & DRONExpo	Cybersecurity Solutions	https://www.zelenza.com/
ZIMPERIUM (United States)	TECNOSEC	Cybersecurity: Cyberdefense and Cybersec, Communications Command and Control	https://www.zimperium.com/

APPENDIX B - TECNOSEC & DRONEXPO CONFERENCES

The following table shows the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo conferences that are relevant to the FCT domain and which have been used in the analysis presented in this report. The full mapping table is available via the [ENACT website](#).

For detailed information regarding the TECNOSEC & DRONExpo conferences please refer to:
<https://www.tecnosec.es/sala-tecnosec/>; <https://www.dronexpo.es/agenda/>

Conference title
The evolution of emergency communication networks towards broadband
Cybersecurity risks and tools in prevention and resilience: risk management planning, ransomware, IoT connectivity, multi-factor authentication, digital identity.
Artificial intelligence in security: automation of crime processes, support in criminology and forensics, processing of large volumes of information
Secure communications from the perspective of encryption, 5G, security and interception.
U-Space: Airspace management and its security implications
Legal-practical impact of the new community regulations (drone navigation)
Anti-drone systems for security and events
Urban Air Mobility

ENACT.

European Network Against
Crime and Terrorism

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